

DESIGN ASPECTS OF A SELECTIVE LEACHING PROCESS FOR SCANDIUM RECOVERY FROM BAUXITE RESIDUE

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Introduction

The exploitation of Bauxite Residue (BR) of Aluminium industry as a resource for production of Rare Earth Elements (REEs), with main focus on Scandium (Sc), seems to emerge as a well promising perspective for a new symbiotic era in the metallurgical processes. Within the European Union (EU) context, this concept is fully aligned with the EU's target for sustainable access to critical raw materials as being of high importance for economy, competitiveness and the environmental protection. BR, either as alkaline wet red mud, or as dried ferroalumina, has to be treated with a leaching process of enhanced selectivity for REEs and of the lower possible yield for the main elements. The liquid leachate product of this process is led to other advanced extraction methods that could enhance their concentration from ppm level to higher percentages.

This work presents the investigation of design aspects for an acidic selective leaching process, which is based on sulphuric acid as leaching agent and it is focused on Sc, because it is the far most valuable trace element of BR and the maximization of its specific recovery (mg Sc/ L of used acid) has been proven to be critical for the process [1]. Simultaneously, the experimental investigation aimed at the lower possible iron (Fe) leaching yields, as long as it is the most abundant cationic element in most of BRs, and especially in examined Greek BR (Aluminium of Greece S.A.), in such an extent that imposes complications to the following enrichment stages. Furthermore, this process preserves the bulk quantity of BR metallic content in precipitated solids and therefore it allows its further metallurgical exploitation.

Design Aspects

The design aspects that have been investigated are analyzed as follows: (i) The selection of process parameters that are considered to affect Sc recovery, (ii) The kinetic investigation for different acid concentrations, (iii) The impact of Liquid to Solids ratio to the Sc leaching yield and its interpretation in the context of chemical reaction engineering, (iv) The experimental verification of the upper limits of Sc

specific recovery with recycling of the leachate in the leaching chemical reactor, and (v) The development of a unified mathematical expression for the Sc leaching yield.

The laboratory experimental investigation of Sc leaching yield with H₂SO₄ solutions has proven significant impact from: (i) Acid feed concentration and the consequently dependent pH value of leachate, (ii) Mixing residence time, if it is lower than 1 hour, and (iii) Liquid to Solids ratio (L/S) in the leaching reactor. However, temperature variation, different agitation modes and selected particle size fractions did not show any significant variation within the investigated range.

The kinetic interpretation of Sc yield data - that were acquired with the use of 12 different acid concentrations and of 5 different mixing times (≤ 1 h) - showed that a first order kinetic approach is valid with sufficient accuracy. The first order kinetic behavior is in accordance with the general thin film diffusion mechanism ([2], eq.(2)). The impact of L/S to the Sc leaching yield was also experimentally investigated, while the interpretation of these data was based on an already proposed mechanism from the field of chemical reaction engineering ([2], eq. (3),(4) and (5)), which combines: (i) The standard mass transfer rate for diffusion of substances (metallic elements) from solid particles to bulk volume of a liquid solvent (i.e., thin film diffusion pattern), and (ii) The un-reacted shrinking core model that is commonly valid in solid particles chemical reactions, with approximately constant external surface area.

The theoretical maximum possible concentration of Sc in the leachate (ppm), for a given Sc concentration in the BR, is a model parameter and a significant process limit, which is estimated by an optimization algorithm to fit to experimental data.

The experimental verification of model predictions, when Sc specific recovery approaches its limits, was implemented by the means of leachate recycling onto fresh BR. These data allowed the further model tuning and led to the development of a unified equation for Sc leaching yield, which shows a quite sufficient predictability level for processing of a raw material (BR) with broadly variable Sc composition.

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References

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